

ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL RESOURCE AS A MODERN DIDACTIC LEARNING TOOL

Bozorova Irina Jumanazarovna

Karshi State University, Lecturer

irisha0426@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6504206>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st April 2022

Accepted: 10th April 2022

Online: 17th April 2022

KEY WORDS

electronic educational resource, didactic tool, educational process, self-study, information and methodological support, educational process.

ABSTRACT

The article discusses the possibilities of using promising achievements in the field of informatization and communication and their implementation in the practice of education, considers new opportunities for the teacher in creating conditions for interaction using electronic educational tools. The use of new pedagogical tools that contribute to the formation of the information and communication environment of an educational organization is also considered.

An electronic resource as a modern didactic tool helps to increase the motivation of students in the context of an increase in the share of independent work. An electronic educational resource includes a set of several functions combined in one didactic tool. An electronic educational resource as a didactic tool is a system-forming element of the process of independent activity of students.

The term "means of learning" in didactics does not have a clear definition and is interpreted in different ways. The means of education, according to researchers, are material means, carriers of educational information, designed to achieve the goals of education.

Didactic teaching aids are classified on various grounds:

- by presence and embodiment: active, passive, background, limited use, disposable, etc.;
- according to the essential content: material, search (synthesis, analysis, recognition, action), managers, individual (role, instruction, leadership), crew (algorithms, prescriptions, situational scenarios), collective (norms, rules, volume, etc.);
- according to the characteristics of the application in the educational process:
 - static (in form, content, location), dynamic (changing in time, educational space), procedural;
 - (action models), recoverable (replicable, reconstructable, modifiable, etc.), transformable (assigned value);
- by specific functions and qualities: (changes, movements), development of

skills, personal reflection (independence of self-esteem, self-awareness, etc.);

- by reflection in physical characteristics: processes and models, algorithms;

- according to the psychophysiological parameters of the trainees: the connection of sensations, teaching methods, variable and flexible logic of presentation and limitation of the flow of information in the face of increasing requirements for the quality of the result;

- performance training and synthesis of protective-executive reactions;

- by relevance: compliance with the requirements of the educational program, operational, tactical, etc.;

- by area of application: local, special, individual, group, etc.;

- for the creative component: solving pedagogical problems in the real process; developed by teachers, synthesized by students, borrowed from outside, etc.

Electronic educational resources as a didactic learning tool are based on the principles of interactivity and practical orientation. Interactivity involves students performing a range of actions: viewing educational material, studying navigation, copying, working with the help system. Practical orientation in all sections and training modules, training tasks of various types, laboratory work, etc.

Didactic teaching aids perform a number of basic general didactic functions:

- increasing the visibility and accessibility of educational material;

- development of cognitive activity, intensification of educational work students, increasing the pace of learning;

- optimization of pedagogical activity;

- management of cognitive activity of students.

In the real educational process, the listed functions of teaching aids are presented systematically, which allows solving the existing methodological problems of teaching.

EER as a didactic tool provides the organization of independent learning activities of students, and includes:

- the structure of educational and methodological material on the discipline (thematic modules in accordance with the goals of educational activities);

- stages of planning and implementation of an individual educational trajectory of a student based on the logic of the presentation of educational material and means of information interaction;

- automated control and self-control;

- interactive dialogue in the "teacher-student" system;

- the possibility of returning to the completed educational material in order to correct knowledge and skills;

- automation of the evaluation activities of the teacher;

- formation of reports on the results of independent activities of students.

The use of electronic educational resources, organizes information interaction based on an interactive dialogue in the "teacher-student" system, automates the control of the results of achieving the goals of education,

implements information and methodological support of the educational process.

In addition, the use of electronic educational resources helps to ensure the individualization of learning, changing the organizational forms of organizing educational activities in the classroom, creating organizational and pedagogical conditions for the development of competencies, skills and abilities of independent work.

Let us dwell in more detail on the problem of formation of independent activity of students in the educational process.

Revealing the content of the concept of independent work, we can note that the active activity of students, which is aimed at achieving a didactic goal, is work that involves formation and development of knowledge, skills and abilities, their generalization and systematization. As a didactic phenomenon, independent activity is a learning task and, at the same time, a form of cognitive activity (memory, thinking, creative imagination) when the student performs tasks, which, as a result, lead to the acquisition of new knowledge

or to the expansion of actions with previously acquired knowledge.

It should also be noted that information activities and independent learning activities are not a set of stage-by-stage organization using information and communication technologies.

The development and use of electronic educational resources must meet the requirements of the integrity of the educational process, the goals of developing the personality of students, the content, forms, methods of teaching.

At the same time, EER should provide methodological and psychological and pedagogical support for educational activities.

An analysis of the approaches and aspects of the integrated use of information and communication technologies in the educational process emphasizes the need to develop information and methodological support for the educational process, which is based on the relationship of educational materials and the implementation of the didactic capabilities of ICT.

The didactic functions of ESM in the educational activities of students can be summarized as follows way table 1.

Table 1
Didactic functions of the electronic educational resource

Didactic function	Characteristic	Means of implementing the didactic function
Accompaniment	Interactive system "teacher-student"	Work program of the discipline, technological map, navigator, recommended literature; reflection of the process and result, evaluation
Education	Mastering the content of	The system of tasks for

	education, the formation of competencies	independent activity
Individualization of learning	Individualization of the educational process, building an individual educational route for students	The variable nature of the tasks of independent work
Reflective	Reflections of the process and result of mastering the discipline	Evaluation of the teacher, the reflexive nature of tasks, point-rating system of evaluation
Information and communication	Ensuring independent activity in an open educational space	Tasks for working with information

The organizational and pedagogical conditions for the implementation of EER as a didactic tool include: regulatory, methodological support, personnel (teachers with a developed information competence).

A special place is occupied by the requirements of methodological expediency and resource provision, which include: regulatory requirements of different levels, software of the educational institution, consistency and sequence of the presented modules (sections), various, effective forms and methods of pedagogical qualimetry of processes intermediate and final certification.

Designing an electronic educational resource includes a preparatory stage and an assembly stage. The first stage is connected with the selection of the main sources of information and the formation of a

system of didactic units of educational content. It is important to note that the selection of the system of didactic units of the content of education clearly reflected the requirements of the work program of the discipline. The second stage is associated with the assembly of the developed components (information, training, control) of the electronic educational resource for demonstration to students in accordance with the developed plan - scenario. When developing the content of an electronic educational resource, the following principles should be taken into account: the priority of the pedagogical approach, modularity, completeness, visibility.

Thus, we can conclude that electronic educational resources are indeed a modern didactic tool for the learning process. Features of designing the learning process with the use of ESM will be considered by us in the second chapter of the final qualification work.

References:

1. Abdeev R.F. Philosophy of information civilization / R.F. Abdeev [electronic resource] URL: <http://filosof.historic.ru/books/item/f00/s00/z0000892/index.shtml>. 04/28/2020

2. Regulations on the organization of the educational process with the use of e-learning, distance learning technologies. Version 2 // Ekaterinburg: UrFU. - 2015. - 267 p.
3. Robert I.W. Modern information technologies in education: didactic problems, prospects for use / I.V. Robert. - M.: IIO RAO, 2010. - 140 p.